

DELIVERABLE

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Manuscript for paper on the solution of one instance of the protein orientation problem

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable is meant to summarise our current conclusions about the cryo-microscopy + OAM sorter experiments. More specifically, we illustrate here how a two-stage OAM sorter allows one to recognise the rotational symmetry as well as the 2D chirality of proteins of interest. Getting information about a protein without actually fully imaging it is one of the main goals of Q-SORT.

This deliverable is one of the partial endpoints of the activities developed so far and takes advantage of task T5.1 (D5.1 and D5.2) and of the sorter itself as developed in WP2. We also use virtual proteins, developed for deliverable D3.3. This deliverable has D5.5, devoted to protein recognition via three-stage or generalized sorter, as its natural continuation.

The deliverable contains 2 parts. The first one is the main manuscript, ideally written for a journal of the Nature publishing Group. The second one is a provisional conclusion that explores the problem of the missing data, the hardware limitations, and improvements, as well as the feasibility of the overall experiments.

IMPORTANT NOTE ABOUT EXPERIMENTS AND COVID-19

Unfortunately, the activities described in this deliverable have been delayed due to technical timing in the delivery of the cryo-blades (D5.2)¹, as well as to the difficulties encountered in the realization of the unconventional configuration. Additionally, when the experimental setup was ready, the travel bans due to the COVID-19 pandemic forced us to interrupt our final run of experiments. This is why the manuscript presented here has partially missing data (as indicated in the text): the actual data is substituted by accurate, high-fidelity simulations done with our custom STEM-CELL software.

At this moment in time the necessary set-up, knowledge, and hardware are ready: therefore, we expect that, as soon as it will be possible to perform the final experiments, the manuscript presented here can be completed with the missing data. These measurements, like all further work in this area, will be presented in D5.5, which is the natural continuation of this deliverable.

¹ As explained in the official Comment accompanying D5.2:

“The deliverable is being submitted now, as we had anticipated in the last Review Meeting, because of the difficulty in procuring and installing the completely custom retractable cryoblades, that had to be redesigned by FEI/Thermo Fisher specifically for the project. The requirement for them to be retractable is very unusual, but necessary in this case because the Titan Holo microscope at Juelich -one of only 2 such machines in the world- has to be used for materials science as well as cryomicroscopy. Fischione (www.fischione.com), the original manufacturer which was slated to design the cryoblades, was chosen when the Project was being written because of its better nominal value-for-money offer. However, once the Project had started and Fischione had received the detailed specifications, their quote changed and as a consequence the Coordinator realised that, if FEI/Thermo Fisher designed and manufactured the cryoblades, this would constitute better value for money. However, since FEI/Thermo Fisher is a Partner in Q-SORT, this required a specific amendment, which took time to negotiate and draft, as well as the standard technical processing time by the EC.

As a consequence, the design work [for cryoblades] started with some delay.

This was compounded by the two-month downtime necessary to install the blades, which was originally scheduled to be a *floating task*, but which due to the above delays became a *critical task* of the Project. Further details on the difficulties encountered in the realisation are given in the deliverable itself.”

Chapter 1: Manuscript

Symmetry and 2D-chirality of a protein measured on a single particle using the angular quantum basis

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The fundamental and counter-intuitive concept that electrons are waves is at the basis of electron microscopy^{1,2}. Electron microscopy permits imaging at scales that are not accessible to light³. Modern microscopy is going beyond imaging and can be seen as a quantum scattering process with a selection of the initial and final state^{4,5}. One of the most spectacular results of electron microscopy is the ability to uncover the intimate atomic structures of delicate biomolecules in cryomicroscopy⁶. Computer-aided reconstructions are based on imaging of many proteins, since a detailed view of a single protein is impossible due to its fast deterioration under beam.

But if, instead of the full imaging, we aim at discovering a specific property of the protein, we can get this even from a single particle. Here we show that the new paradigm of analysis based on unitary transformations of the wavefunction (in this case the Orbital Angular Momentum sorter^{7,8,9}) can be used to distinguish the n-fold symmetry of a single protein and/or its upside-down orientation. We use here an innovative idea of virtual protein image/wavefunction generated by SiN holograms to be compared with real ones in a real cryo-experiment.

The method is different from imaging exactly in the fact that, in a different quantum basis, the little information extracted that is allowed by the limited dose is concentrated on a specific characteristic, while less important details, like in-plane orientation¹⁰, are lost in the non-measured phase of the wavefunction. This, in general, can be a stand-alone analysis for fast identification of protein structures with different symmetries or can be put in the context of conventional cryo-microscopy reconstruction as a way to obtain specific information for a faster and more detailed 3D reconstruction.

In quantum mechanics, one of the advantage of the Heisenberg matrix mechanics with respect to Schrodinger approach is that Heisenberg gives a more general vision of the wavefunction beyond a

single basis or representation¹¹. Electron microscopy, instead, is still mainly based on imaging and therefore on spatial representation of the wavefunction.

If real space imaging is the main feature of an electron microscope, maybe the most successful refinement of this idea has been cryo-microscopy for the analysis of dose sensitive proteins. Here multiple instances of the same object, embedded in a layer of vitreous ice, are imaged in random orientations to compose a single averaged 3D reconstruction. This idea allows the 3D reconstruction of dose sensitive objects, e.g. proteins, within an acceptable amount of electron dose per particle. The limited information accessed through a single image is merged, but this does not solve the problem at the level of a single protein.

The work we would like to do is generalizing from image to any representation of the wavefunction to optimize the concept of measurement. However, still space representation appears to have a privileged role in quantum measuring and the root of this seems to lie at the foundation of quantum mechanics itself¹². For example, we are still mainly bound to measure position (imaging), momentum (diffraction) and energy (EELS) in terms of spatial dispersion.

The recent addition to this list is the Orbital Angular Momentum (OAM) sorter that permits wave transformation so that on the camera the Orbital Angular Momentum decomposition can be directly read. For practical applications, the OAM sorter can be considered as an additional set of thin lenses breaking the cylindrical symmetry of the microscope. While recently an OAM sorter was built based on SiN hologram, here we use a set of electrostatic elements¹³ that have the advantages of tunability, precision, and, most of all, almost no loss in the electron intensity and therefore nearly unitary transformation in the quantum mechanical sense. This has large importance for the analysis of dose sensitive materials where every spent electron matters.

The electrostatic implementation is based on a needle in the first phase element and a periodic array of electrodes in the second phase element. Complex set of phase plates or lenses, in a broad sense, beyond the cylindrical symmetry have indeed been implemented a few times in electron microscopy to obtain improvements like the spherical aberration correction¹⁴ and energy spectrometer.

Fig. 1 The new microscope configuration with electrostatic optical elements biased externally. The Sorter phase elements inserted in are shown in b, c (the first element) and d, e (the second element). A test hologram (f), its coordinate transformation (g) and the OAM- P_r spectrum are also shown (h) and (i) after averaging.

The peculiarity of the OAM sorter is that, given a coordinate in complex notation $u=x+iy$, it carries on the conformal transformation $U'=\ln(u)$. Fig. 1 shows the new electrostatic optical elements capable of carrying on the transformation and its ability to measure the decomposition of a test beam generated by the hologram in Fig. 1g.

The important measured quantity here is the Orbital Angular Momentum. In a system of axes where the electron propagates along the z direction the quantum mechanics operator is defined as $L_z = -i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta}$ where θ and ρ is are the phase and module of u . To complete the set of observables of this radial basis, we find here the logarithmic radial momentum $P_r = -i\hbar \rho \frac{\partial}{\partial \rho}$. L_z is the generator of the in-plane rotations - its application produces a rotation $R = \exp(i L_z \delta\theta)$. In an object with m -fold symmetry a rotation by $\delta\theta = 2\pi/m$ leads to the same wave function and this means that the spectrum of L_z is made only of multiples of m .

This means that the symmetry of the object is directly visible as a main feature of the spectrum potentially with few electrons. In this work, we dedicate to the ESX-1 secretion-associated protein B (EspB) from *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*¹⁵ that exhibits, when seen from top, a well-defined symmetry, usually seven-fold, given by the repetition of the amino-acid sequence. There exist, even in the same sample, many variants of the same protein with 6 or 8-fold symmetry. Moreover, each protein can be present with opposite orientations at the air-water interface and it would be a very important contribution to be able to distinguish between the two orientations in order to facilitate the full protein reconstruction.

In this experiment, we initially simplify the problem and instead of using a real protein, we use a virtual protein produced by a hologram. The hologram is obtained by sculpturing a thickness modulation in a thin membrane of SiN^{16,17,18}. This object is, to a good approximation, a phase-only object, namely an object whose main effect is to modulate the phase of the electron wave passing through it, similar to what a real protein does, only reported on a scale of 100 times larger.

This has the advantage to make the conceptual experiment more affordable. In fact, the smart use of a-priori information helps to produce the partial gain of information per electron implicit in this method. The main a-priori information is the accurate positioning of the protein at the center of the optical axis.

This is at the moment not possible on a precise protein before destroying it. However this can be carried out by scanning or randomly collecting spectra in different positions. We will use this possibility later in this paper.

Figure 2 shows the experiments performed using 3 different virtual proteins. The first two possessing 7-fold symmetry but opposite orientations, while the third is the case of protein with a 6-fold symmetry. Finally, the 4th is a model of spiral “protein” that will come handy for the discussion.

For the protein, the ball-and-stick models are reported in the first column of each of the first 3 rows. The next columns show the real space image of the proteins both in and out of focus. In the 4th column, a log-polar representation of the protein, obtained through the sorter, is shown, while finally the OAM – radial momentum representation, namely the final outcome of the sorter diffraction, is shown in the 5th column. The 6th column is the OAM spectrum alone.

Whereas relatively weak, the L_z component 6 and 7 are clearly different in the two cases. It is more complicated to tell apart the difference between the up-down orientation. In fact it can be appreciated only as a non-separable radial-OAM peak.

In fact, if the OAM alone is observed, the spectrum is nearly perfectly symmetric, but if the radial dispersion is also observed, there is a clear asymmetric feature of spirals¹⁹ that have function of $\varphi = m\theta + f(r)$. To exemplify this we studied experimentally the wave $\psi = A\cos(m\theta + a\rho)$. This is a hologram²⁰ of a perfect spiral in the hologram plane, producing a superposition of Bessel beams in Fresnel and a vortex ring beam in Fraunhofer.

This is a perfect example of where the asymmetry comes from since it produces a perfectly symmetric OAM spectrum but two peaks that are indeed shifted along the radial momentum direction. The non-separable state is therefore written as

$$\psi = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}|\ell = \ell_0 \rangle |P_r = p \rangle + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}|\ell = -\ell_0 \rangle |P_r = -p \rangle$$

Where the center of symmetry of P_r is defined by the barycenter of the OAM $-P_r$ spectrum .

This effect is not 3D chirality since this is a 2D property related to the projected potential of the protein, but can be transformed in 3D chirality with appropriate propagation and post-selection. For a 2D projection still can be defined 2D chirality²¹ since in a 2D world the object transformed upon mirror reflection cannot be brought to be coincident with itself by rotation and translation. Inspired by this we can define the quantity roughly related to 2D chirality as

$$X(\ell) = \frac{\sum_{p < p_0} (\langle \psi | \ell = \ell_0, P \rangle - \langle \psi | \ell = -\ell_0, p \rangle)}{\sum_{p < p_0} (\langle \psi | \ell = \ell_0, P \rangle + \langle \psi | \ell = -\ell_0, p \rangle)}$$

And using this quantity we can distinguish the up and down orientation. We find a value of X in the protein at the $|\ell|=14$ to be as large as 25%. For example, this can be done also in the experiment with the virtual protein where we find a similar result. Given the intensity of this component we calculated that a dose of $1e/\text{\AA}^2$ that is a statistically tolerated dose is sufficient to single out this characteristic property.

Fig. 2 Experimental test of the OAM sorter on the virtual proteins. The virtual structure of the protein is shown in the first column, the TEM image of the actual hologram in focus and out of focus are featured in column 2,3. The protein after conformal mapping is shown in column 4. The 5th column is the OAM-Pr spectrum. The image has been color enhanced to show fainter details. The 6th is the OAM spectrum alone obtained by averaging vertically from column 5. The first two rows refer to the 7-fold symmetric protein with opposite orientation. The third is a protein with 6-fold symmetry. The fourth row is an abstract spiral object aimed to demonstrate the spiral phase effect on the OAM-Pr spectrum. **DATA ON OAM SPECTRA 5th and 6th COLUMN WILL BE AVAILABLE AFTER COVID, SIMULATION ARE USED INSTEAD**

As a final experiment, we demonstrate the use of the OAM sorter with actual proteins showing the full advantage of the method. The experiment combining the use of an OAM sorter and cryo-microscopy setup is completely new and unique. For comparison, we show in Fig. 3 the typical protein image and we find that, in standard cryo-TEM images, the symmetry of the protein and let alone the up-down orientation cannot be easily discerned from a single image.

The image on the left side is one of the randomly sampled image, and the corresponding OAM spectrum shows clearly the peak at OAM equals 7. Since such a strong peak cannot appear as an effect of the protein misalignment (see supplementary), it cannot be doubted that this is a clear marker of the 7-fold symmetry of the protein obtained where normal single particle imaging fails to prove.

Fig. 3 a) Experimental conventional cryo-microscopy image of the protein EspB, b) OAM- P_r dispersion (dose $1 \text{ e} / \text{\AA}^2$), (c) P_r averaged OAM spectrum of a protein selected by random sampling. The points indicate the periodicities at $|\ell|=7$ and $|\ell|=14$.

FIG B,C are simulations REAL DATA WILL BE AVAILABLE AFTER COVID

We also found a X value of **DATA WILL BE AVAILABLE AFTER COVID** that can be unambiguously used to discern the up orientation. To conclude we have demonstrated our ability to go beyond the standard imaging in cryo-microscopy using a different representation based on the OAM sorter. Using this different representation, we were able to capture the main characteristic of the proteins like 2D chirality, n-fold symmetry and orientation that would not normally be evident on a level of a single protein imaging. While normal cryo-microscopy gains information through exploring different protein orientations, we have gained specialized information by exploring a different representation and therefore prospecting even a statistical tomography in the phase space.

References

- 1 E. Ruska: The Electron Microscope as Ultra-Microscope. In: Research and Progress. Band 1, (1935), S. 18–19
- 2 J Harris, et al. Structured matter waves Nature Physics 11 (2015) 629
- 3 Jiang, Y., et al. Electron ptychography of 2D materials to deep sub-ångström resolution. Nature 559, 343–349 (2018).
- 4 Giulio Guzzinati et al Probing the symmetry of the potential of localized surface plasmon resonances with phase-shaped electron beams Nature communications 8 (2017) 1
- 5 Matteo Zanfagnini, et al. Orbital angular momentum and energy loss characterization of plasmonic excitations in metallic nanostructures in TEM ACS Photonics 6 (2019) 620
- 6 R. Henderson, The potential and limitations of neutrons, electrons and X-rays for atomic resolution microscopy of unstained biological molecules Quart. Rev. Biophys. 28, 171 (1995)
- 7 V. Grillo et al. Measuring the orbital angular momentum spectrum of an electron beam, Nat. Comm. 8, 15536 (2017).
- 8 G. C. Berkhout et al. Efficient sorting of orbital angular momentum states of light. Phys. Rev. Lett. 105,

153601 (2010).

9 B. J. McMorran T. R. Harvey, M. P. J. Lavery Efficient sorting of free electron orbital angular momentum New J. Phys. 19, 023053 (2017)

10 Troiani et al. Efficient molecule discrimination in electron microscopy through an optimized orbital angular momentum sorter <https://arxiv.org/abs/2001.08918>

11 F. A. Muller, The equivalence myth of quantum mechanics; Part I: Stud. Hist. Phil. Mod. Phys. 28(1), 35–61 (1997); Part II: Stud. Hist. Phil. Mod. Phys. 28(2), 219–241 (1997)

12 Wojciech H Zurek k Decoherence, einselection, and the quantum origins of the classical Rev. Mod. Phys. 75, (2003) 715

13 A. H. Tavabi, Experimental demonstration of an electrostatic orbital angular momentum sorter for electrons. Preprint at <https://arxiv.org/abs/1910.03706>

14 Maximilian Haider et al. Electron microscopy image enhanced. Nature, 392,768 (1998).

15 Solomonson M, Setiaputra D, Makepeace KAT, Lameignere E, Petrotchenko EV, Conrady DG, Bergeron JR, Vuckovic M, DiMaio F, Borchers CH, Yip CK, Strynadka NCJ. , Structure of EspB from the ESX-1 type VII secretion system and insights into its export mechanism. Structure 23, 571 (2015).

16 V. Grillo et al. Highly efficient electron vortex beams generated by nanofabricated phase holograms Appl. Phys. Lett. 104, 043109 (2014).

17 Shiloh, R., Lereah, Y., Lilach, Y. & Arie, A. Sculpturing the electron wave function using nanoscale phase masks. Ultramicroscopy 144, 26–31 (2014).

18 Harvey, T. R. et al. Efficient diffractive phase optics for electrons. New J. Phys.16, 093039 (2014).

19 Yuanjie Yang, G. Thirunavukkarasu, M. Babiker, and Jun Yuan1, Orbital-Angular-Momentum Mode Selection by Rotationally Symmetric Superposition of Chiral States with Application to Electron Vortex Beams Phys. Rev. Lett. 119, 094802 (2017)

20 Grillo, et al., Generation and application of Bessel beams in electron microscopy, Ultramicroscopy, 166 (2016) 48-60.

21 Oriol Arteaga et al Relation between 2D/3D chirality and the appearance of chiroptical effects in real nanostructures Optics Express 24, 2242 (2016)

Chapter 2: Provisional conclusions

2.1 Hardware improvements

In the work so far the sorter has demonstrated to work reasonably well. The provisional spectrum in Fig. 3 is a simulation assuming a limited dose of $1e/\text{\AA}^2$.

Fig. 4. Early experiments. Two spectra are obtained in what we discovered later to be vacuum. Still this is the best spectrum so far in terms of quality of sorter alignment.

By comparison, we show here two early experimental spectra. These spectra were obtained when trying to scan on a protein, but after a second check we discovered that the sample was destroyed due to the problem in the cryo-module. Still, we can use this data as the best data on OAM sorting so far. They highlight a relatively small background oscillation that decreases with OAM. An ideal sorter would feature a sinc function with a width of $\Delta\ell=1$. In reality, the peak here is $\Delta\ell=1.3$ wide and the secondary peaks more or less at $\ell=3$ are 8% of the central peak.

In order to further improve the result, we are working on an automatic alignment procedure that controls all TEM commands, as this would allow to better observe tiny features in the spectra.

While at the moment the analysis is at the limit of the potentiality of the sorter, PSF (point spread function) processing /deconvolution will be necessary, after an accurate alignment, for us to work with clean untreated data.

As for hardware improvements, we show here in Fig. 1 the new version of the OAM sorter with 6 independent electrodes and a double connection for the main tip. The 6 connections are necessary because the previous versions based on the electrostatic mirror showed problems. In particular, the

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mirror was too thin in z-direction with respect to the main length of the needles. Our results indicate a better sorting even with relatively large convergences (4.5 mrad) and therefore an overall better sorting at every angular range.

As anticipated, the main needle is biased through 2 independent contacts. This detail permits, while controlling the applied voltage, to apply a current that heats the tips and largely avoids contamination. This appliance enhances the lifespan of the sorter and strongly improves the quality and reproducibility of the results over time.

A third improvement has been the use of a remotely controlled generator that is able to set all the voltages applied to a maximum of 16 contacts. This will be very useful for the automatic alignment procedure that we aim to produce. In the meanwhile, we developed a Labview GUI to drive the 16 contacts and to ease the manual alignment procedure.

Fig. 5 Front panel of the sorter control tool.

Finally we applied a different unconventional lens setup that permitted to have a larger magnification of the OAM spectrum even without using the GIF filter.

2.2 Feasibility

There are two features we want to see. One is the 7-fold periodicity that has relatively large visibility. The intensity should be about 5-10% of the main peak and therefore comparable with the oscillation still present at the moment. Since these oscillations are largely reproducible, a deconvolution should allow their removal and the actual detection of the peaks at $|\ell|=7$ works even at the present working conditions.

There is hope also to see the signal on actual proteins -- the improvement of the alignment procedure by automatic algorithm is expected to strongly help in this respect.

The second feature is the 2D chirality. This requires the detection of a fainter asymmetry at the peak at $|\ell|=14$. While we are sure that we can see this with a very accurate experiment on virtual proteins (with virtually unlimited signal-to-noise ratio), the actual feasibility on real proteins remains uncertain, given the difficulty of correctly aligning the protein main axis with that of the sorter. As explained **in the manuscript** a 'scattershot sampling' approach should ensure that a certain percentage of examined proteins is aligned with sufficient accuracy to effect the measurement

In conclusion, we are very confident of the efficacy of this novel approach on virtual proteins. As to its application to real proteins, we are waiting for the possibility to continue our experiments in the upgraded Titan Holo, which we already used to take real-space TEM images of the molecules (Fig. 3 (a)). As explained in the introduction, we were forced to interrupt our experiment there due to travel bans caused by the COVID-19 pandemic. As soon as travel conditions allow it, we will resume the experiment, and thus test this approach on real molecules.

ANNEX 1: Referee

Referee 1

The work is very promising and I think it will really be an outstanding paper if all the box of missing data are filled. What is the delay that you expect on the timeline of the deliverable so far ?

It really depends on the COVID. In principle even a single session of 5 days could be enough to close this deliverable. We have reserved the microscope in April and June but have no idea of the actual feasibility. As obvious we live a moment of great uncertainty.

What is the final journal you would like to submit to in the best scenario?

The paper is meant for a journal like Nature Methods or Nature Communication. All depends on the quality of the final data.

I think you should give more detail of the fabrication of holograms, of the data treatment and so on.

In the final paper that would be in the methods section. The details are anyway quite standard and similar to our previous work in ref 7 and 12.

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Regarding the OAM sorter how long will it take for you to write the optimization and control software.

If the situation remains what it is for 2 months we can finish the first version of the control software but cannot try it on the microscope. CNR and FZJ are now working very much on this idea.

Referee 2

I know this work is suffering of many problems related to COVID , GIF and Cryoblades problems, still I must suspend the judgment waiting for the final version of the paper/deliverable. I appreciate all the hardware improvements that are certainly a great step considering that each of these steps is absolutely new in electron microscopy and that there is much to be discovered.

When will the next version of this paper will be ready in realistic time?

If the COVID situation improves we could have a near final draft by mid-summer.

ANNEX 2: ABBREVIATIONS**SHORT NAME OF PARTICIPANTS**

Partner	Country	Short Name
National Research Council (Project scientific coordinator)	Italy	CNR
Forschungszentrum Jülich, Ernst Ruska-Centre for Microscopy and Spectroscopy with Electrons	Germany	FZJ
FEI - Thermo Fisher Scientific	The Netherlands	FEI
The Max Planck Institute for the Science of Light	Germany	MPI
University of Glasgow, Department of Physics and Astronomy	United Kingdom	UG
QED Film & Stage Productions Ltd. - UK	United Kingdom	QED
University of Modena and Reggio Emilia, Department of Physics, Informatics, and Mathematics - IT	Italy	UMR
Maastricht University, Maastricht MultiModal Molecular Imaging Inst	The Netherlands	MU

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Consortium Agreement	CA
Description of Action	DoA
Description of Work	DoW
European Commission	EC
Grant Agreement	GA
Kick-off Meeting	KoM
Project Management Board	PMB
Work Package	WP
Work Package Leader	WPL

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